

The Effects of Situational Teaching on Preschool Children’s Originality Development

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 06 January 2022	Preschool education is a critical stage in a child's life. Several studies have confirmed that the pivotal moment for the development of creativity is between the ages of three and five. Through cultivation, training, and learning development ability, preschool children's creativity can be amplified through the presence of nature and the imagination of instructional strategies. The purpose of this research is to look into the effect of situational learning in physical education on preschool children's creativity. This study's methodology begins with a pre-test of the child's creativity performance, followed by a six-week program of situational physical learning lessons. The data is compared to show how children's learning abilities have changed and how effective situational learning training has been in increasing creativity.
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KEYWORDS: Situated learning, physical education, creativity, Originality, imagination.	

INTRODUCTION

According to Zhou Yuru (2012), the infancy stage is the physical and mental development of a person's life. The Early Childhood Educare (2017) takes a fresh look at early childhood education by focusing on free and guided play learning. Children are playful by nature, and through situational games and participation, they can progressively develop new skills to perform appropriate roles within groups. A variety of playful scenarios can help children develop their emotional and cognitive needs, as well as their individual development. Play-induced social behaviors can encourage positive interactions and values set in social connections, according to Zhang et al. (2010). Previous studies has created much relevant discussion and research, as well as introduced the notion of situational learning, which is becoming increasingly commonly recognized by the public for use in a range of learning activities and knowledge-emphasizing learning (Brown et al., 1989). Other research has shown that data gathering should take place in context-based cognitive learning tasks (Lave & Wenger, 1991). The learning process necessitates instructors attempting a variety of strategies in order to keep the child engaged in various situations and environments in order to develop interest in learning at an early infancy level (Huang, 2007).

Using narrative circumstances in physical education-related games for preschoolers, according to Zhang and Huang (2005), produces a pressure-free learning atmosphere, and the

variety of activities would stimulate kids to learn. Letting two or more toddlers to participate in situational cognitive games can improve interpersonal interactions and collaboration prospects (Liao and Huang, 2016). Students would learn about the notion of togetherness, innovative thinking, and becoming more inventive as they worked to complete the task.

Situational learning, according to Jamali, Kazemi, and Shahbazi (2012), might help toddlers acquire and apply knowledge, as well as increase their creative thinking abilities, in settings when there is no physically or emotionally pressure. It has been shown that a crucial period of creativity development occurs between the ages of 3 and 5. Children's creativity may be encouraged through environmental design and educational activities through developing, training, and acquiring development abilities (Johnson et al., 2005; Zhang, 2008; Zhou, 2011; Wei, 2014; Song, 2016).

The concept of education for preschoolers is gradually shifting in a constantly changing environment, and this study mainly investigates if context-sensitive physical educational game lessons could help preschool children to develop their reasoning and problem-solving skills with the ability to keep up with the ever changing future of mankind.

METHODOLOGY

The focus of this research is to see how a six-week situational sports game teaching approach affects the creativity of

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preschool children by repeating Torrance's creativity prediction test (1981). With the permission of the parents, preschoolers kid then participates in the situational physical education curriculum. A pre-test, which comprises activities creative performance stimulation exam on 'Originality,' also known as the ability to come up with a solution independently without outside assistance, is to be undertaken in order to record the children's growth. The reliability test yielded a result of 0.75, which falls within the acceptable range of 0.60 to 0.76.

There are five steps to the experiment:

- 1) a physical warm-up; 2) a plot is presented, and the student is asked to relate the story to previous classes; 3) the story is acted out with costumes and props using the scenario supplied to the student;
- 4) A variety of interactive activities were carried out with praises to encourage students to be more vocal; 5) To gradually de-escalate the student's fun feeling, music is played along with a similar warm-up activity, with the instructor praising each student's performance at the conclusion.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The before and after of a 6-week situational physical education game lesson can be seen in the figure below. The gathered information on experiment participants' originality is compared before and after the test. The material of the action and action creation thinking tests was used to create the interview data.

In Figure 1, the children were first test on their originality in coming up with ideas and solutions to cope with the given scenario. During the pre-test, group A had the highest score of all the groups, earning a total of 40 points. Groups C, D, and E received 24, group B received 13, and group F received 6. Suggesting on how the nature of how different toddlers are different from their natural attributions. The six-week program in situational physical education learning techniques aims to boost the preschoolers' creativity, allowing them to come up with better solutions to the problem at hand.

Figure 1. Pre-Test Results: Originality

In Figure 2, all preschoolers have increased their capacity to identify what the provided narrative is about and are able to come up with original solutions by themselves to deal with situation of the story after only six weeks of situational physical education instruction. From the data, Group D has the greatest degree of originality, with a score of 65, followed by group C with 64, group E with 60, group B with 53, group A with 46, and group F with 26.

Figure 2. Post-Test Results: Originality

Figure 3 shows how situational physical education learning approaches may increase toddlers' creativity in understanding the directions, difficulties, and stories offered by the instructors by comparing pre and post test results. Group D (+41), group C (+40), group B (+40), group E (+36), group F (+ 20), and group A (+6) demonstrated the most noticeable gains. It is worth noting that, although group A demonstrated the least degree of growth in their originality level after six weeks of instruction (46), even though they scored the highest during the pre-test. Possible explanation might be that group A is already familiar with coming up with original ideas to defuse the situation, however possible stubbornness may limited certain groups originality, as some students may think, one solution fits all type of scenarios. The remainder of the groups are unfamiliar with the notion of situational learning, and it is possible that this fresh undiscovered territory is what kept groups B,C,D,E, and F engaged and emerged from this experiment. Group F had the lowest pre-test and post-test scores, which might be explained by the fact that the group may require more time and exercise to achieve better progress.

Figure 3. Comparison of Pre and Post Test Results: Originality

CONCLUSION

The effects of situational physical education learning has proven effective on the growth of preschool children. As seen that during the pre-test, the children have scored a range from 6 to 40. Suggesting that by default some children are not creative enough to use their experience or surrounding to come up with strategies on their own to resolve the task. However after the six0week of training, the test results showed that the children are becoming more aware of the assignment and are more capable of developing original ideas to deal with the situation. Still the learning capability of each individual is different, for instance, the score of group A was previously 40 had merely improved to 46, possible that group A would assume that the lessons are some concept that are repetitive or already known. It would be more of recommendation if the child would be taken to a more advance situation for further observation of progress.

According to the statistics presented, there is a need for each kid to locate a proper study setting, and teachers must constantly modify study surroundings to keep preschoolers engaged to learn. The significance of creativity in fluently understanding the external environment status may assist improve a child's critical thinking, which will boost prospective innovation, social interaction, and cooperative abilities at a later age. For nations suffering dropping birthrates, it has become a race for preschoolers to achieve at an early age. As per findings, the practice of situational physical education learning could bring potential and boost to preschooler's originality.

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